

ROLE OF SSA IN ACADEMIC SKILL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Country is passing through major economic developments with the liberalisation and globalisation of the economy. Academic skill is a tool that can play a vital role in improving the socio-economic condition of the nation. It empowers citizens with analytical abilities, leads to better confidence level and fortifies one with willpower and goal setting competencies.

Key words: SSA, Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, drop out rate, schools

INTRODUCTION

The framework of Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan includes appointment of teachers, their training, motivating parents and students, provision of incentives like scholarships, uniforms, textbooks etc. The programme also aims to open new schools in areas having inadequate schooling facilities and strengthen existing school infrastructure through the construction of additional classrooms provision of toilets, drinking water facilities and so on.

Problems Relating to Drop Out

There are problems relating to drop out rate, low level of learning achievement and less participation of girls, tribal and other disadvantaged of groups. There are still at least one lakh habitations in the country without schooling facility within a kilometre. Coupled with it are various systematic issues like inadequate school, infrastructure, poorly functioning schools, high teacher's absenteeism, large numbers of teachers' vacancies, poor quality of education and inadequate funds.

The country is yet to achieve the exclusive goal of universalisation of elementary education, which means 100% enrolment and retention of children with schooling facilities in all habitants. It is to fill this gap that the Government has launched the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan.

The SSA is a historic stride towards achieving the long cherished goal of universalisation of elementary education through a time bound integrated approach in partnership with state. SSA, which promises to change the face of the elementary education sectors of the country, aims to provide useful and quality elementary education to all children in the six to fourteen age groups. The SSA is an effort to recognise the need for improving the performance of the school system and to provide community owned quality elementary education in mission mode. It also envisages bridging of gender and social gaps.

The SSA Works

The SSA works on a community based approach to planning with habitation as a unit of planning. Habitation plans will be the basis for formulating district plans. It will not disturb existing structures in state and districts but only try to bring convergence in all those efforts. Efforts will be made to ensure that there is functional decentralisation down to the school level in order to improve community participation. There is a focus on the educational participation of children from scheduled caste and tribe religion and linguistic minorities disadvantaged groups and the disabled children. SSA is commence throughout the country with a well planned pre-project phase that provides for a large members of intervention for capacity development to empower the delivery and monitoring system.

SSA plays a special interest on making education useful and relevant for children by improving the curriculum, child centred activities with effective planning methods.

It provides quality education including life skills. It also seeks to provide computer education to bridge the digital divide.

Poor families are not able to afford the fees charged in private schools that charge relatively modest fees and poor children also attend some of the schools are marked by poor infrastructure and low paid teachers. While encouraging efforts at equity and 'access to all' in well-endowed private unaided schools, striving areas of public-private partnership were also made.

Government, local bodies and government aided schools were covered under the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan. More than 34,000 schools were aided over the last five years almost 30 percent of the 1.2 million schools in India. Schools churned out more than 17 million students eligible for higher education in 2008-09, three times the number five years ago. Similarly, 14.2 million children joined schools in 2008-09, increasing the enrolment to over 206 million about 96.4 percent of the child population. A 15 percent increase over enrolment percentage of 80, when the programme started in 2001. World bank has also called the SSA “World’s most successful programme”. Over 200 million children now go to school, double the number a decade ago. The programme has made the millennium development goal of ensuring that every child goes to school by 2020, look achievable.

COCLUSION

While elementary education in India has received a shot in the arm through SSA, there are not enough institutions, to meet the demand for higher education and vocational training .There is a need to create a programme similar to SSA for higher education also in India.